

COMMUNITY BEHAVIOR AND OUTREACH COMMUNICATION IN COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Lukman Hakim

Lecturer in Public Administration, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar

E-mail: lukman.hakim@unismuh.co.id

Abstract

The main focus of this research is the lack of implementation outreach communication in community behavior in the Covid-19 pandemic. Extension communication as an approach is an effort to increase motivation, awareness, and empowerment of the quality of human resources (people-centered development). The purpose of this study is to examine the approach and development of extension communication in accelerating community behavior in breaking the Covid-19 chain. This research method was a qualitative research approach to analyze in-depth the content of information sources regarding outreach activities and community behavior in Covid-19 transmission. Primary data collected were obtained through observation and in-depth interviews that involved 106 informants in 90 villages at 18 districts/cities of South Sulawesi. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained by tracing documents at the Covid-19 service post in South Sulawesi Province. The results show that people's behavior is the discipline in maintaining cleanliness and health during the Covid-19 pandemic, but they are still worried and anxious and have less interaction pandemic. Education and government motivation through outreach communication to the community to change behavior is well obeyed by the community.

Keywords: *Behavior, Communication, Education, Covid-19*

PRELIMINARY

South Sulawesi Province is a red zone in the number of positive *Covid-19* patients in Indonesia. South Sulawesi Province is ranked 3-4 in the number of positive cases of the coronavirus or COVID-19 in Indonesia. The accumulation until mid-July 2020, the number of positive patients in South Sulawesi until July 21 2020 is 7470 cases or 8.3% of the national number of cases (Ministry of Health, 2020). Various actions have been taken to break the chain of the spread of Covid-19, among others self-isolation for those who experience symptoms of coronavirus infection, especially in the last 2 weeks that the patient has been in an area that infected by Covid-19 case or has had contact with a Covid-19 sufferer that cause new symptoms to raise which require them to stay at home for 14 days and limiting contact with other people. Another action is the policy of the South Sulawesi Provincial government by implementing Large Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in several districts/cities so that the community can limit their socio-economic activities both among people within the city itself

and their interactions with other regional communities, so this prohibition will affect activities both local and national economies in all sectors of economic and industrial activity both on the land, sea and in the air.

Covid-19 data in South Sulawesi by July 21, 2020

Source: Secondary Data, 2020

Independent isolation for the sufferers and Large-Scale Social Restriction (PSBB) policies in districts/cities influence reducing patients in treatment and increasing healing. However, the number of Man Under Surveillance (ODP) and patients under surveillance (PDP) is still increasing every day. According to Buana (2020), one factor that trigs the increase in Man Under Surveillance (ODP) and patient under surveillance (PDP) are the behavior of people who lack disciplines such as presence in a crowd, lack of social distancing, less wearing masks, lack Personal protective equipment (PPE), lack of shelter for medical personnel, medical personnel fatigue factor, and the difficulty of detecting Man Without Symptoms (OTG) who participate in transmitting the virus to both their family and other people. Therefore, this study examines people's life behavior in the Covid-19 pandemic and how extension communication effort is a strategic way of breaking the COVID-19 chain.

Extension communication through increasing motivation, awareness, empowerment, leadership, and improving the quality of human resources is not optimally implemented either by the village / sub-district government or at the district/city level. Extension communication as one of the approaches is intended as the effort to develop human resources (people-centered development) in the context of social development through approaches that are more respectful of human dignity (humanization) that in line with various regional government policies in breaking the chain of COVID- 19 transmission. One of the reasons is because the socialization of policies is short and does not reach public awareness and motivation in changing behavior to break the chain of Covid-19. Therefore, this research is also aimed to study the importance of outreach development description.

LITERATURE REVIEW

State Of The Art

Coronavirus or *severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)* is a virus that attacks the respiratory system. This disease due to viral infection is called Covid-19. The coronavirus can cause minor disorders of the respiratory system and severe lung infections that can lead to death. Coronavirus is a new type of coronavirus that is transmitted to humans. Although it attacks more the elderly (older people), this virus can attack anyone, baby, children, up to adults, including pregnant women and breastfeeding mothers.

Limbong in Saputra (2020) states "Coronavirus (Covid-19) is a single-stranded RNA virus that comes from the Coronaviridae group. It is called coronavirus because of its surface shaped like a crown (crown/corona). Another virus that belongs to a similar group is the virus that caused Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS-CoV) several years ago. " Covid-19 is contagious and spreads very fast ((Merry Dame Cristy Pane, 2020 in <https://www.alodokter.com/virus-corona>) and has spread to almost all countries including Indonesia, in just a few months. Countries implement policies *lockdown* to prevent the spread of the Coronavirus. In Indonesia itself, a social restriction policy is enforced to break the chain of transmission of COVID 19. However, if the social restrictions are long enough and not in line among the cities, it will be a mess and the losses will be even greater both economically and socially (Hadiwardoyo, 2020).

Community Behavior in Facing Disease Outbreaks

Community behavior towards disease prevention is generally lacking (Cipta, 2015). Many people do not respond to the government's appeal to break the chain of transmission of Covid-19 which is stated by Buana (2020) as a cognitive bias, namely the way people think that tends to be wrong in making decisions. Another tendency for cognitive bias is that people pay less attention to events around their environment and influencing the way they perceive and think about the world (Haselton, Nettle, & Andrews, 2005) although it can help a human understand the world and reach decisions at relative speed (Kahneman, 2011). Thus, people who are less willing to follow the government's appeal and feel that they better understand the virus are categorized as having a cognitive bias. One of the facts of the lack of understanding of the virus is visiting a place that provides a comfortable and pleasant feeling to control emotions during a pandemic (Blanchette, 2010) and they feel smart enough to protect themselves outside the home. According to Kahneman (2011) several things that need to be done in overcoming cognitive bias, namely:

1. Every decision must be accurate and not taken under pressure in a short time.
2. Every decision must be made maximally by focusing more on one type of work,
3. Every decision is taken in a state of better feeling and cognition, especially in the morning, so that it will maximize the decisions that will be taken.
4. Everyone who makes decisions must be able to control feelings of positivity so that they can detect mistakes that will occur.
5. Every decision must be supported by the existence of data and facts from every condition that occurs so that the results are sharper and broader and can minimize mistakes.

Thus every action during the Covid-19 pandemic must be carried out carefully for the safety of the entire community so that the virus can soon end in human life.

Infection Control and Prevention Steps

Infection control and COVID-19 prevention include several actions namely:

1) individual quarantine for those who have interacted with Covid-19 sufferers, especially for people who come from countries with high COVID transmission. Therefore, experts assess that quarantine of individuals is one step to control the spread of Covid-19 to reduce the spread of respiratory viruses, 2) improving hand hygiene compliance inpatient treatment. Hand hygiene is considered an effective preventive measure and compliance with hand hygiene can reduce the rate of infection related to health care, 3) using personal protective equipment (PPE) to prevent highly contagious diseases due to exposure to contaminated body fluids to health workers. In epidemics of highly contagious diseases, such as Ebola, severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), or coronavirus (Covid-19), health workers are at a much greater risk of infection than the general public, due to their contact with patients' contaminated bodies and fluids. Personal protective equipment (PPE) can reduce risk by covering exposed body parts. A new respiratory tract infections spread, such as during the Covid-19 pandemic, health care workers' compliance with infection prevention and control (IPC) becomes more important, including the use of personal protective equipment such as masks, face shields, gloves, and gowns among patients, patients with tighter cleaning routines, and 4) using of respiratory protective equipment (RPE) as a preventive measure. RPE can help provide protection when used properly and when removed safely, as well as when it replaced or regularly maintained (gloves and gowns separate among patients with a more stringent cleaning routine. (<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/collections/doi/SC000040/full>).

It was also necessary to keep mental health by instilling positive values in people's lives. Therefore a positive psychological approach is very important to maintain a healthy mentality and has implications for life satisfaction and happiness so that it can boost the immune system and warding off the coronavirus outbreak (Van Leeuwen, et al., 2012. and Barak, 2006). Life happiness according to Victor Frankl (1984) is related to a person's ability to understand the meaning in life. and are more prepared and stronger in dealing with other traumatic events in the future (Calhoun, et al., 2010).

Public health

Public health status is influenced by four factors, namely: 1) environment, 2) behavior, 3) health services, and 4) heredity (Blum in Yustina, 2003). According to Blum's research, the environment has the greatest share of public health status. However, in developing countries, especially Indonesia, the behavior is believed to have the greatest contribution to public health status. If human behavior is clean and healthy, it is expected that the environment will be healthy. To change human behavior, education is the answer (Prastiwi, 2019). Education is a learning process that is believed that able to change human behavior in the health sector, to behave based on the demands of health values such as being proactive in maintaining and improving health (physical activity and eating with balanced nutrition), preventing the risk of disease, protecting oneself from the threat of disease and have an active role in the community movement.

Outreach Communication

Outreach is an activity to provide information or enlightenment to individuals or groups so that human behavior which includes knowledge, skills, and attitudes is getting better and qualified. Outreach is non-formal education to invite people to be willing to implement new ideas (Mulyana, 2007: 11). Outreach is also an activity to educate people about something, giving them new knowledge, information, and abilities, so that they can form attitudes and behave in life according to what they should be (Nasution, 1989). As a practical action, outreach is an effort made to encourage behavior change in individuals, groups, communities, or communities so that they know, want, and can solve the problems they are facing (Amanah, 2007). Outreach communication aims to improve the quality of human life both morally and

materially through increasing motivation, empowerment, leadership, and the quality of human resource behavior. The development of outreach communication also aims to improve the quality of community behavior effectively, foster initiative and motivation to change oneself for the better, take initiative and be innovative in developing community participation so that it becomes a dynamic society. Therefore, outreach communication is a medium to improve the quality of human behavior which serves to stem the false information circulating amid Covid-19. The spread of false information through information technology can disrupt people's social life, it makes the public faced with split views when the information conveyed turns out to be different from the actual conditions. The condition of the community that tends to ignore and without trying to find the truth of the news that is circulating, even participating in spreading false information (hoax) has raised concerns among many circles. Previous research by Rianto in Saputra (2020) revealed several reasons why parties spread hoax information. These answers include that the information disseminated becomes viral so that it can change or influence public opinion, the desire to change government policies that are deemed inappropriate, provide support to certain elements of society to business competition. Most the circulated information is untrue and do not base on the facts, Allah SWT said in Surah Al-Isra verse 17: "And do not follow something that you do not know. Because of hearing, sight, and conscience, all of that will be held accountable." (Masykur, 2014). The awareness process is an important and very decisive element in handling social problems (rief Machmudy 2015). If the awareness process is successful, surely people with social problems will find it easy to overcome the problem, because they know exactly the depth of the problem they have, their potential and abilities, their resources, the direction and goals to be achieved, and the results of happiness. to be achieved (Tampubolon, 2006). Thus in this context, counseling is not only the delivery of knowledge information but a movement for public awareness to make changes, where all people are positioned as subjects who jointly make changes (Rubawati, 2018).

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted in South Sulawesi, which is a district/city that is in the red zone with Covid-19. The selection of the research location was determined purposively (purposive sampling) with the consideration that the region was a Covid-19 pandemic case that continues to increase in 90 villages in the districts/cities of South Sulawesi. The community members in this village had characteristics and diversity in responding and behaving in the Covid-19 pandemic in the last 5 months from February to July 2020. The research locations were as in table 1 below:

Table 1. Village Locations of Informants

No.	Regency / City	Village / Sub-district	
1.	Makassar	1. Mangala	6. Edge of the Land
		2. Buakana	7. Tammua
		3. Tamalanrea	8. Rappocini
		4. Jongaya	9. Maccini Sombala
		5. Tamalate	
2.	Gowa	1. Tubaseng	8. Bontonompo
		2. Look forward	9. Julumate'ne
		3. Parangloe	10. Limbung
		4. Pallangga	11. Parangloe
		5. Somba Opu	12. Pacellekang
		6. Mangalli	13. Kalase'rena
		7. Sungguminasa	14. Biringngala

3.	East Luwu	1. Leddu-Leddu 2. Lumbewe 3. Laro	4. Tomoni 5. Bantilang 6. Kalatiri
4.	Jeneponto	1. Bontonompo 2. Maero 3. Panaikang 4. Arungkeke	5. Fort 6. Tamalatea 7. Binamu
5.	Areca	1. Makkawaru 2. Ulu Saddang 3. Pekkabata	4. Buttu Sawerang 5. Patampanua 6. Leppongang
6.	Maros	1. Gattareng	6. Tanuntung
7.	Bulukumba	1. Tugondeng 2. Bonto Bahari 3. Hill of Hope 4. Somba Palioi 5. Bulukumpa	7. Polewali 8. Tanah Jaya 9. Tanete 10. Bontomaccinna
8.	Sinjai	1. Saotengah 2. Lambolemo 3. North Sinjai	6. Tanete
9.	Bone	1. Palattae 2. Turicinnae 3. Laburasseng 4. Kalero 5. Polewali	7. Waetuwo 8. Tana Batue 9. Fur Alla 10. Sanrego
10.	Enrekang	1. Alla 2. Cakke 3. Enrekang	4. Patongloan 5. Salongge
11.	North Luwu	1. Sidomukti 2. Pao	
12.	Pangkajene islands	1. Lanne 2. Pallaboreng 3. Samalewa	
13.	Bull	1. Campagaloe	
14.	Takalar	1. Patani 2. North pods	
15.	Soppeng	1. Laringgi	
16.	Selayar	1. Citadel	
17.	Wajo	1. Alausalo 2. Alewadeng	3. Goodsamase 4. Alelebboe
18.	Barru	1. Invite East 2. Coppo 3. Walk	4. Palakka 5. Tanete Riaja

Source: Primary Data, 2020

Research analysis deployed qualitative analysis by using triangulation in obtaining information sources (Raco, 2018) included regarding people's behavior in coronavirus transmission. A qualitative approach was an in-depth analysis of the content of community behavior and the carried out counseling and the quality of control and preventive steps taken. Primary data collected were obtained through observation and in-depth interviews with 106 informants in 90 villages at 18 districts/cities of South Sulawesi. Meanwhile, secondary data

was obtained by tracing documents at the Covid-19 service post in South Sulawesi Province. All data obtained were analyzed for their correlation with primary and secondary data obtained from informants (Martono, 2010).

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Community Behavior

The behavior of people amid the Covid-19 pandemic can be known from their knowledge of Covid-19. As many as 88.6% of people in 90 villages at 18 districts/cities know about the Covid-19 pandemic from social media, TV, posters, and local government socialization and education. Meanwhile, 11.4% stated that they are still unfamiliar with the dangers and threats of Covid-19 and are not aware of any calls to implement health protocols such as social distancing, washing hands, wearing masks, and disinfectants.

The Covid-19 pandemic brings great concern to the community, namely not knowing how long this condition will last. As many as 94.3% of the people are very worried about the current situation because of the difficulty of earning money, many have experienced layoffs and there is a lot of horrendous news about the disease so that they are afraid to go everywhere and automatically stop working. Others worry less is about their families who are migrating far from their hometowns and cannot return and their livelihoods must be disturbed. Therefore, personal and family safety is the main thing so all family members do not infect by the virus.

As many as 66.9% of people feel confused about what they have to do and do not, staying at home is the right choice at this time. Many companies in the industrial, manufacturing, and other sectors stop or limit their activities, resulting in the phenomenon of workers being laid off or workers being subject to salary cuts. Likewise, traders who depend on their income from their daily sales. Market traders, vegetable vendors, street vendors to traders with bigger shops are affected by the social restrictions imposed by the local government. However, some of those who work as farmers can work more calmly and continue to work as usual because their conditions are still safe and still comply with health protocol rules.

As many as 96.7% of people have an important attitude to maintain a clean environment to live healthily and avoid disease. Each house has water and soap in front of each house to wash their hands and objects around them before entering the house and also have to wear a mask when going out of the house for important needs. However, those experiencing economic problems prefer daily necessities to buy hand soap, hand sanitizer, masks, and other medical devices recommended by the government. Public awareness of maintaining health, especially food consumption that should be maintained is the highest desire to consume water to strengthen the immune system in the body. As many as 91.5% of the public stated that they regularly consume water to prevent dehydration and do not cause a dry feeling in the throat. As many as 80.1% stated that they regularly consume vegetables and fruit so that the immune system is stronger and is not exposed to the Covid-19 virus. People in the village mostly have their vegetable gardens and even though the market is closed, they can still consume vegetables even more often because they do not have food and other side dishes. They also know that consuming vegetables and fruit is the best source of fiber for health. Although there are 19% of people who consume less fruit and vegetables due to limited traders and high prices. Public knowledge of the benefits of vegetables and fruits which contain lots of vitamins and minerals needed by the body still needs to be improved so that they have a higher immune system to prevent infection due to the coronavirus. In addition to consuming healthy food, exercise is also important, such as jogging and sunbathing. Sports activities are beneficial to keep the body healthy, boost the immune system, and make the body's metabolism increase. The types of exercises that are carried out are cycling, jogging and afternoon gymnastics, so that during the Covid-19 period, sports activities are important for the community to maintain health and

fitness and stamina. However, only 64.1% of the people in the survey areas are active in sports and some others are more concerned with work, so during the Covid-19, sports activities are important for the community so that they could maintain health and fitness and stamina.

People become active in their fields or to move their bodies and sunbathe in the morning. 67.9% of people feel anxious about Covid-19 are not being able to interact. Media news that scares the public and is considered to have exaggerated information even though they think Covid-19 can be prevented by a healthy lifestyle with good nutritional intake. They are also anxious because they cannot interact with other communities and are not used to the rules of maintaining distance. Therefore, their anxiety and stress are balanced by playing cards, playing sports, and watching TV at home. During Covid-19, they cultivated crops in their respective yards and gathered with their relatives. 61.3% stated that they could entertain themselves to reduce boredom and boredom at home during the Covid-19 pandemic. Although some people can entertain themselves at home, they still carry out productive activities using the available time and can control emotions in their family and other neighbors. Only 29.2% of the people admitted that they are irritable and less productive because of the economic crisis that triggered debates in the family and neighbors. Meanwhile, 70.8% of them remain calm and continue to do things that become daily routines accompanied by health protocols. For those who go to school and college, they continue to carry out their activities online and work from home. 2% of people admit that they are irritable and less productive because of the economic crisis that has triggered debates in the family and neighbors.

Some other people prefer to work and do activities outside the home to make a living. In a pandemic like this, the economic sector has experienced a decline, and the expectation of assistance from the government, it is still insufficient. They consider that this plague is a lesson for the future to maintain health and get closer to the creator. They are also increasingly creative and foster an entrepreneurial spirit outside of their routine activities. However, for people who work as Civil Servants, teachers, sub-district employees, and sub-district employees use the work from a home method.

Economic difficulties during the Covid-19 pandemic did not prevent people from donating to help other communities. As many as 84.9% of the community donated to the need, both in the form of money and necessities. Some others have communication to help residents who need help and together with the village government carry out a COVID assistance program for each household, especially those who are elderly and less fortunate. Various community organizations, school alumni made donations during the Covid-19 pandemic. They see donation as a moral way, such as reminding each other and praying for the safety of everyone. Donations from political parties are also given to the community during the campaign for regional head elections.

Business activities or shopping during Covid-19 did not go well and smoothly because traders/sellers felt a loss and required their sales to be closed and return to their hometowns, except for the groceries who could still survive to open. The large-scale social restriction (PSBB) policy also paralyzes traders who supply agricultural products such as corn, beans, and rice because the circulation of money in their business is not going well. As many as 52.8% stated that their business activities or spending in the village had stalled and for several weeks had stopped. The informant's statement can be seen in table 2 below

Table 2. Percentage of Informant Statements in the Village District / City

No.	Statement	Percentage (%)
1.	Knowledge about COVID-19.	88.6
2.	Bringing concerns to the community.	94.3
3.	Feeling confused and unable to do work.	66.9

4.	The community is more concerned about cleanliness and health.	96.7
5.	People often consume water.	91.5
6.	People consume more vegetables and fruit.	80.1
7.	People in the village exercise more often during COVID-19.	64.1
8.	People in the village feel anxious and less interaction with other communities.	67.9
9.	Entertaining by playing cards, exercising, and watching TV at home during COVID-19.	61.3
10.	Family and neighbors are irritable and less productive during COVID-19.	29.2
11.	Donating aid to underprivileged people.	84.9
12.	Business activities or community shopping during COVID-19 are going well and smoothly.	52.8
13.	The government suggestion asks the public to be disciplined and vigilant as long as COVID-19 is obeyed by the community.	92.4
14.	The government educates or motivates people to change their behavior to be healthy and clean.	91.5
15.	Outreach communication to the community to change behavior into healthy and clean behavior.	88.6
16.	<i>Social distancing, work from home</i> , as well as the prohibition on going home, from the government it is conveyed explicitly to the public.	85.8
17.	Spreading the Covid-19 guideline book.	21.6
18.	The village government is preparing a COVID-19 service post.	90.5

Source: Primary Data, 2020

Outreach Communication

Outreach communications in the form of government recommendations in the village continue to ask the public to be disciplined and vigilant during Covid-19. As many as 92.4% of the community obey this recommendation and order workers to work from home and always apply health protocols, although some others have not been able to change their behavior and are not obedient because they continue to work as usual to survive. As many as 91.5% of the community responded well to the education and motivation of the government in the village which is carried out together with health workers as a form of concern for the village government so that this epidemic does not continue. Education and motivation are carried out in mosques in each district and village. Traveling for education through health education for clean living. A total of 88, 6% of the community stated that the government in the village intensify communication and outreach to the community to change their behavior to healthy and clean behavior and distribute personal protective equipment (PPE) to residents so they would not be infected by the virus. Communication and counseling are carried out under the coordination of the local government, TNI-Polri officers, the health team, the COVID group, and others who continue to visit each house announcing healthy, clean living habits. The role of the media is very helpful for the village government in conveying social distancing, work from house, and prohibition of going home. The recommendation is accompanied by sanctions and if proven to have violated the homecoming will be ordered to return home or be quarantined at the destination and a post is provided for those who violate it. Every traveler who comes from out of town must report to the Covid-19 response task force such as local

medical personnel or show a COVID-free letter in the form of a report on the results of a rapid test from a referral hospital for COVID patients. This assertiveness is well responded to by the community and if there is no assertiveness, then the community will continue to commit violations. Community obedience is supported by socio-cultural conditions as local people who have blood relations with each other.

The efforts to educate the public about Covid-19 or other outbreaks are not supported by the availability of reading material in the form of a Covid-19 pocketbook which should have caught the attention of the government with the available budget support. As many as 78.4% of the people in the survey areas have never received a book about Covid-19. This is quite concerning considering the large budget allocated by the government in dealing with Covid-19. Meanwhile, the district government itself is easier to provide education through mass media and social media. The slowdown in the transmission of Covid-19 at the district level cannot be separated from the role of the Covid-19 service post in each village. This service post makes it easier for COVID officers to record and monitor village residents. A total of 90, 5% of people think that service posts can anticipate the coronavirus and provide services and checks to the public. Likewise, students and volunteers collaborated with the village government in socializing the prevention of Covid-19 as well as spraying disinfectants in every resident's house.

CONCLUSION

1. The behavior of the public is disciplined in maintaining cleanliness and health in the Covid-19 pandemic, but they are still worried and anxious and have less interaction during the Covid-19 pandemic.
2. People still feel irritable and less productive behavior during the Covid-19
3. Donation for the affected community continues in the form of food and cash.
4. Community business or shopping activities during the Covid-19 are running well and smoothly
5. Education and government motivation through outreach communication to the community to change behavior is well obeyed by the community.

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